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<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>

Шавази Наргиз Нуралиевна

DSc. доцент, заведующая кафедрой акушерства и гинекологии N 3 СамГМУ.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>

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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428

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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327

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ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523

Ибрагимовна Малика Худайбергандовна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор Ташкентского государственного стоматологического института
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры онкологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503

Даминов Феруз Асадуллаевич

Декан лечебного факультета №2 Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, доктор медицинских наук, доцент. Самарканд, Узбекистан.

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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9309-3933

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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

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ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

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*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute,
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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327.*

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ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

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YUSUPOV Jasur Tolibovich

Assistant

MATLUBOV Mansur Muratovich

DSc, professor

Samarkand State Medical University

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ABSTRACT

Among the leading causes of death in the adult population, coronary heart disease (CHD) is one of the foremost. Both international and Russian guidelines for the treatment of CHD recommend a collaborative approach when selecting surgical revascularization, particularly coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG). Generally, CABG can be performed using two types of surgical interventions: one with cardiopulmonary bypass (CPB) and cardiac arrest, and another on a beating heart without CPB. The key difference between these approaches lies in the use of CPB and the stoppage of the heart during surgery in the first method, while the second involves surgery on a functioning heart. Both surgical interventions and the use of CPB activate the complement system and trigger the release of cytokines, leading to a systemic inflammatory response. IL-6, IL-1b, and tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF-a) are the primary mediators of the acute phase of the inflammatory response. Analysis indicates that the early postoperative administration of ulinastatin inhibits the sequestration and activation of neutrophils, reduces the typical postoperative rise in cytokine levels, and alleviates systemic inflammatory response syndrome, pulmonary microvessel permeability, and postoperative pulmonary edema.

Key words: coronary heart disease, coronary artery bypass grafting, artificial blood circulation, cytokines, ulinastatin, systemic inflammatory reaction syndrome.

ЮСУПОВ Жасур Толибович

Ассистент

МАТЛУБОВ Мансур Муратович

Д.м.н., профессор

Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет

**УЛУЧШЕНИЕ ИНТЕНСИВНОЙ ТЕРАПИИ ПАЦИЕНТОВ ПОСЛЕ
АОРТОКОРОНАРНОГО ШУНТИРОВАНИЯ**

(ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ)**АННОТАЦИЯ**

Среди причин смертности взрослого населения ишемическая болезнь сердца (ИБС) занимает одно из ведущих мест. Международные и российские рекомендации по лечению ИБС требуют коллегиального подхода к выбору метода хирургической реваскуляризации как аортокоронарное шунтирование (АКШ). В целом, АКШ с включенной помпой и без нее - это 2 типа хирургических вмешательств, разница между которыми заключается в использовании системы искусственного кровообращения (ИК) и остановке сердца для проведения операции во время АКШ с включенной помпой и операции на работающем сердце. Хирургические вмешательства и ИК - это медицинские состояния, которые вызывают системную воспалительную реакцию, активируя систему комплемента и запуская выброс цитокинов. IL-6, IL-1b и фактор некроза опухоли-альфа (TNF-a) являются основными медиаторами острой фазы воспалительных реакций. Анализ показывает, что использования улиностадина в раннем послеоперационном периоде ингибирует секвестрацию и активацию нейтрофилов и ослабляет нормальное послеоперационное повышение уровня цитокинов, уменьшая синдром системной воспалительной реакции, проницаемость микрососудов легких и послеоперационный отек легких.

Ключевые слова: ишемическая болезнь сердца, аортокоронарное шунтирование, искусственное кровообращение, цитокины, улиностадин, синдром системной воспалительной реакции.

YUSUPOV Jasur Tolibovich

Assistent

MATLUBOV Mansur Muratovich

DSc, professor

Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti

**AORTOKORONAR SHUNTLASHDAN KEYINGI BEMORLARDA INTENSIV
TERAPIYANI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH
(ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI)**

ANNOTATSIYA

Katta yoshli aholi o'limining sabablari orasida yurak ishemik kasalligi (YIK) yetakchi o'rinlardan birini egallaydi. Yurak ishemik kasalligini davolash bo'yicha xalqaro va Rossiya tavsiyalari aortokoronar shuntlash (AKSh) kabi toj tomirlarni jarrohlik revaskulyarizatsiyasiga birgalikda yondashuvni talab qiladi. Umuman olganda, aortokoronar shuntlash 2 turdagi jarrohlik aralashuvlaridan iborat bo'lib, ularning orasidagi farq sun'iy qon aylanish tizimidan (SQA) foydalanib, paralel SQA bilan birga to'xtatilmagan yurakda hamda yurakni to'xtatib va ishlaydigan yurakda operatsiya qilishdir. Jarrohlik aralashuvlari va sun'iy qon aylanish — bu komplement tizimini faollashtirish va sitokinlarning chiqarilishini boshlash orqali tizimli yallig'lanish reaksiyasini keltirib chiqaradigan tabiiy holatdir. IL-6, IL-1b va o'sma nekrozi faktori alfa (TNF-a) yallig'lanish reaksiyalarining o'tkir bosqichining asosiy vositachisidir. Tahlil shuni ko'rsatadiki, operatsiyadan keyingi erta davrda ulinostatinni qo'llash neytrofillarning sekvestratsiyasi va faollashuvini pasayishini hamda sitokin darajasining operatsiyadan keyingi normal o'sishini susaytiradi, tizimli yallig'lanish reaksiyasi sindromini, o'pka kapillyarlarining o'tkazuvchanligini va operatsiyadan keyingi o'pka shishini kamaytiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: yurak ishemik kasalligi, aortokoronar shuntlash, sun'iy qon aylanish, sitokinlar, ulinostatini, tizimli yallig'lanish reaksiyasi sindromi.

Dunyo bo'ylab aholining kasallanishi va o'limining asosiy sababi yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari hisoblanadi. Yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari tarkibida eng katta ulushni yurak ishemik kasalligi (YIK) tashkil etadi, u esa kattalar o'limining asosiy sabablaridan biri bo'lib qolmoqda [5,9]. Jahon sog'liqni saqlash tashkilotining (JST) hisob-kitoblariga ko'ra, har yili dunyoda yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari

sababli 17 milliondan ortiq odam vafot etadi, ulardan 7 milliondan ortig'i yurak ishemik kasalligi sababli o'ladi. Yurak ishemik kasalligi dunyo bo'ylab erkaklar va ayollar o'limining asosiy sababidir [12,16]. Amerikaning yurak assotsiatsiyasining ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, 15 milliondan ortiq odam turli shakllarda ushbu kasallikka chalingan. Jahon amaliyotida hozirda eng dolzarb masalalardan biri bo'lib, yangi biomarkerlarga qaratilgan fundamental tadqiqotlar davom etmoqda. Bu biomarkerlarga molekulyar biologiyada qo'llaniladigan va hujayradagi barcha patofiziologik jarayonlar bilan bog'liq bo'lgan, shuningdek, o'tkir va surunkali yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari rivojlanish mexanizmlarini ochib beruvchi tadqiqotlar kiradi [5,8,11].

Yurak ishemik kasalligi kasallanishining o'sishi, nogironlik va aholi o'limining yuqori ko'rsatkichlari bilan bog'liq ravishda, kasallikni davolash usullarini takomillashtirish masalasi zamonaviy kardiologiyaning eng muhim vazifalaridan biridir. So'nggi o'n yilliklarda kasallikni davolashdagi taraqqiyot kardiojarrohlik rivojlanishi bilan bog'liq. Keng tarqalgan kardiojarrohlik aralashuvlaridan biri bo'lib, aortokoronar shuntlash, mammarokoronar shuntlash va teri orqali aralashuvlar (ballon angioplastikasi va koronar arteriyalarni stentlash) qo'llaniladi [3,4]. Yurak ishemik kasalligi bilan kasallangan bemorlar - ancha geterogen guruh bo'lib, ularning yarmidan ko'pi ko'p tomirlar shikastlanishi bilan ajralib turadi va bu esa ularni yanada murakkab va og'ir bemorlar kategoriyasiga kiritadi [9].

Har bir revaskulyarizatsiya usulining o'z ko'rsatmalari va afzalliklari mavjud. Xalqaro va Rossiyaning yurak ishemik kasalliklarini davolash bo'yicha tavsiyalari jarrohlik revaskulyarizatsiya usulini tanlashda jamoaviy yondashuvni talab qiladi. Asosiy jarrohlik davolash ko'rsatmalari koronaroangiografiya, noinvaziv va invaziv tekshiruv usullarining ma'lumotlari asosida, klinik holat va qo'shimcha patologiyalarni hisobga olgan holda aniqlanadi [4,11]. Yomon natijalarga olib keladigan yurak-qon tomir hodisalarining xavfini kamaytirish maqsadida, toj tomirlar shikastlanishining anatomik xususiyatlari, qo'shimcha kasalliklar va operatsiya xavfini hisobga olish muhim [6,11]. Aortokoronar shuntlash (AKSh) zamonaviy kardiojarrohlikda keng tarqalgan operatsiyalardan biridir. Unga ko'rsatilgan asosiy ko'rsatmalar quyidagilar: yurak ishemik kasalligini endovaskulyar davolash usullarining (ballon angioplastikasi va stentlash) samarali bo'lmasligi, chap koronar arteriyaning 50% dan ortiq torayishi, ko'plab koronar arteriyalar torayishi, oldingi interventrikulyar arteriyaning markaziy arteriyadan chiqish joyida kritik torayishi, III-IV funksional sinfda barqaror stenokardiya, dori vositalari bilan tuzalmaydigan barqaror bo'lmagan stenokardiya hisoblanadi [2,4,11].

Aortokoronar shuntlash (AKSh) — bu yirik jarrohlik amaliyoti bo'lib, unda bemorning koronar arteriyalaridagi ateromatoz to'siqlar venoz yoki arterial kanallar yordamida o'tkazib yuboriladi. Shuntlash jarayoni ishemik miokardga qon oqimini tiklaydi, bu esa o'z navbatida yurak funksiyasini tiklash, jonli ekanligini saqlab qolish va stenokardiya simptomlarini bartaraf etishga yordam beradi. Har yili deyarli 400 000 ta aortokoronar shuntlash amaliyoti o'tkaziladi, bu uni eng ko'p amalga oshiriladigan yirik jarrohlik amaliyoti qiladi [1,2]. Biroq, jarrohlik aralashuvlariga bo'lgan talab, dori vositalari bilan davolash va teri orqali aralashuvlar kabi alternativ variantlarning qo'llanilishi kengayishi bilan pasaygan. Ushbu tadqiqot aortokoronar shuntlash uchun ko'rsatilgan ko'rsatmalarni tasvirlab beradi va yurak ishemik kasalligi bilan kasallangan bemorlarni davolashda ko'p sohalar mutaxassislarining rolini ta'kidlaydi [1,7].

Umuman olganda, aortokoronar shuntlashning sun'iy qon aylanish apparati yordamida va sun'iy qon aylanish apparatisiz ikki turi mavjud bo'lib, ular orasidagi farq sun'iy qon aylanishi tizimidan foydalangan holda aortokoronar shuntlash apparat bilan bajarilgan holatda yurakni to'xtatib (ya'ni kardioplegiyabilan) yoki parallel yurakni to'xtatmasdan operatsiya qilishda, shuningdek, ishlab turgan yurakda bajariladigan operatsiyalarga bo'linadi. Avvalgi yillarda sun'iy qon aylanishi tizimi qo'llanilmagan operatsiyalardan so'ng, bemorlarda kamroq miqdorda nevrologik asoratlar, kognitiv buzilishlar kuzatilgan, kamroq qon quyish talab etilgan va tizimli yallig'lanish belgilarining kamroq bo'lishi qayd etilgan [7,13]. Afilalo J. va hamkorlari o'zlarining 59 ta tadqiqotni (taxminan 9000 bemor) o'z ichiga olgan meta-tahlilida aorta koronar operatsiyalarining ikkala texnikasini solishtirishgan [11]. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, sun'iy qon aylanishi tizimisiz operatsiya qilingan bemorlarda operatsiyadan keyingi serebrovaskulyar asoratlar 30% past bo'lgan, va o'lim darajasi

hamda miokard infarkti bo'yicha farqlar yo'q edi [5,8]. Meta- tahlilida klinik natijalar, bemorning yoshi, tadqiqotdagi ayollar ulushi va shuntlar sonidan qat'iy nazar bir xil bo'lgan [6]. Forouzannia S.K. va hamkorlari (2011) ham sun'iy qon aylanishi tizimi qo'llanilgan va yurak ishlayotgan holda o'tkazilgan operatsiyalarining klinik va iqtisodiy natijalarini solishtirishgan. Mualliflar jarrohlik asoratlarining tezligi bo'yicha statistik jihatdan ahamiyatli farqlar mavjud emasligini ta'kidladilar. Tadqiqotning asosiy xulosasi shuki, sun'iy qon aylanishi tizimi qo'llanilgan operatsiyalar sezilarli darajada qimmatroq bo'lgan [2].

SQA (sun'iy qon aylanishi tizimi)da o'tkazilgan amaliyotlar davomida deyarli 40 yil davomida yurak ishemik kasalligini jarrohlik davolashning "oltin standarti" bo'lib qolgan. Biroq, 1980-yillarda SQA bilan bog'liq tizimli yallig'lanish reaksiyasi, ko'p organlar yetishmovchiligi va o'lim holatlari aniqlangach [3], ushbu usulning xavfsizligi haqida shubhalar paydo bo'ldi. Sun'iy qon aylanishining bir qismi sifatida gemodilyutsiya, gipotermiya va antikoagulyatsiya kiritiladi. Ushbu komponentlar klinik jihatdan muhim oqibatlar va asoratlar bilan bog'liq bo'lib, shu jumladan koagulopatiyalarni o'z ichiga oladi. Yurakdagi operatsiya yakunida og'ir qon ketishi, gemodilyutsiya bilan bog'liq bo'lgan gemostaz tizimidagi buzilishlar va uning ortiqcha faollashishi tufayli yuzaga keladi. Asoratlar rivojlanishi xavfi sun'iy qon aylanishini ikki soat davomida qo'llanilganda oshadi, va uch-to'rt soat davomida foydalanish natijasida sezilarli darajada ortadi [6]. Bu qonning o'zgarishi, kapillyarlar membranasining o'tkazuvchanligining buzilishi va to'qimalarning keyingi gipoksiyasi bilan bog'liq asoratlar sonining ko'payishiga to'g'ri proporsionaldir. Sun'iy qon aylanishi qo'llanilgandan so'ng, ko'p organlar yetishmovchiligi bilan bog'liq klinik, biokimyoviy va radiologik belgilarning to'plami aniqlanadi.

Sun'iy qon aylanishidan foydalanishning eng keng tarqalgan nojo'ya ta'sirlari kolloidlarning qon tomir ichidagi onkotik bosimini pasayishi, trombotsitlarning shikastlanishi va plazmaga vazoaktiv moddalarning chiqarilishi [7,9]. Boshqa keng tarqalgan nojo'ya ta'sirlar orasida organizmdagi gidrobalansi va siydik ajralishi buzilishi, gipertenziya, yurak-qon tomir tizimi funksiyalarining buzilishi, koagulopatiyalar, elektrolitlar bilan bog'liq buzilishlar, serebral disfunktsiya (emboliya yoki ishemik buzilishlar), komplement va neytrofil tizimining faollashishi, mikroemboliyaning xavfini oshishi, buyrak qon oqimini shikastlanishi hamda nafas olish va oshqozon-ichak tizimi funksiyalarining buzilishlari mavjud [2,6].

Sun'iy qon aylanishidan foydalanish, plazma oqsillari, leykotsitlar va endoteliy hujayralarining faollashuvi orqali tizimli yallig'lanish javob reaksiyasini keltirib chiqaradi. Bu o'z navbatida leykotsitlar va endoteliy hujayralari o'rtasidagi o'zaro bog'liqlikni o'rnatadi; leykotsitlar qon tomirlaridan chiqadi, sitokinlar sekretsiyasi yuzaga keladi, trombotsitlar va neytrofilarning faollashuvi, ularning degranulyatsiyasi va endoteliy funksiyasining buzilishi ro'y beradi [2,4,7]. Bundan tashqari, sun'iy qon aylanishidan foydalanish va undan keyin sitoplazmada metalloproteinazalar sintezlanib, qon tomirlariga chiqadi. Sitoplazmatik metalloproteinazalar — bu ekstrasselulyar matriksni (hujayralar va ularning funksiyalari uchun zarur bo'lgan) parchalovchi fermentlar oilasiga kiradi va to'qimalarning shikastlanishiga olib keladi. Bu o'zgarishlar hujayra va molekulyar darajada sun'iy qon aylanishidan foydalanish natijasida yuzaga keladi va operatsiyadan keyingi poliorgan yetishmovchiligiga olib kelishi mumkin, natijada esa o'lim darajasi va operatsiyadan keyingi asoratlar rivojlanishining ko'payishiga olib keladi [6,8].

Sitokinlar — bu yallig'lanish va hujayralar o'sishini tartibga soluvchi ko'plab eruvchan oqsillar va peptidlarning umumiy nomi. Sitokinlar interleykinlar, monokinlar, limfokinlar va interferonlarga bo'linadi. Yaqinda yangi sitokinlar sinfi — xemokinlar ajratib olindi, ular neytrofillarning faollashuvi va xemotaksis jarayonlarida ishtirok etadi [7,10]. Deyarli barcha hujayralar, qon tomirlarining shikastlanishga javob sifatida biologik reaksiyalarida ishtirok etuvchi, turli stimullarga javoban o'ziga xos ta'sirga ega bo'lgan oqsillarni ajratib chiqarishi mumkin. Agar biologik faol moddalarning sekretsiyasi lokalizatsiya qilingan bo'lsa, ular o'sish va differentsiya jarayonlarida muhim rol o'ynaydi. Agar sitokinlar darajasi tizimli aylanishda oshsa, masalan, sepsis, shok yoki sun'iy qon aylanishi holatlarida, bu organizm uchun og'ir oqibatlarga olib keladi.

Sun'iy qon aylanishiga javoban diffuz sitokinlar reaksiyasi so'nggi 20 yilda olib borilgan ko'plab tadqiqotlarda namoyish etilgan, chunki alohida oqsillar aniqlanib, o'rganilgan. Ba'zi

tadqiqotlarda sitokinlar ishlab chiqarilishi darajasi o'lim darajasi va asoratlar soni bilan korrelyatsiyalanganligi ko'rsatilgan. Sitokinlar asosiy o'rinda umumlashgan yallig'lanish javob reaksiyasida ishtirok etadi, bunda qon ekstrakorporal tizimdan bemorning qon aylanish tizimiga qaytadi. Pro-yallig'lanish sitokinlari ishlab chiqarilishining oshishiga qo'shimcha ravishda, ko'plab tadqiqotlar sitokinlar reaksiyalarining nazoratining buzilishi haqida guvohlik bermoqda [15,17]. So'nggi tadqiqotlarga ko'ra, aortokoronar shuntlashda asoratlarning rivojlanishi, ehtimol, yallig'lanish sitokinlarining haddan ziyod ishlab chiqarilishiga qarshi turishga qodir bo'lmagan yallig'lanishga qarshi sitokinlarning yetishmasligi bilan bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin.

Sitokinlar ishlab chiqarishdan mas'ul hujayralarda ularning o'zi kamdan-kam hollarda to'liq shakllangan holda bo'ladi. Aksincha, ularni ishlab chiqaradigan hujayralar avvaliga plazmadagi himoya oqsillari yoki kamaygan to'qima perfuziyasi bilan faollashishi kerak. Ushbu stimullarga javoban hujayralar yangi oqsillar — sitokinlar ishlab chiqaradi. So'ngra ular hujayralardan chiqariladi. So'nggi 10 yilda qon tomirlar biologiyasi sohasidagi tadqiqotlar asosan hujayralarni faollashtirish va sitokinlar ishlab chiqarishga olib boradigan signallar va jarayonlarni o'rganishga qaratilgan edi [12,15,17].

Jarrohlik aralashuvlari va sun'iy qon aylanishi — bu tizimli yallig'lanish reaksiyasini keltirib chiqaradigan tabiiy holatlar bo'lib, komplement tizimini faollashtiradi va sitokinlarning ajralib chiqishini boshlaydi [1,4]. IL-6, IL-1b va o'sma nekrozi faktori-alfa (TNF-a) yallig'lanish reaksiyalarining o'tkir fazasining asosiy mediatorlaridir. Eksperimental tadqiqotlarning natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, sitokinlar ishlab chiqarilishining oshishi bir nechta fiziologik tizimlarning barqarorligiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin [5,6]. Insonning yurak to'qimasida IL-6, IL-2 va TNF-a salbiy inotropik ta'sir ko'rsatadi [3]. Perioperatsion davrda sitokinlarning ajralib chiqishi yurak jarrohlik amaliyotini o'tkazgan bemorlarda yurak-qon tomir tizimining barqarorsizligi bilan bog'liq ekanligi ko'rsatilgan. Hozirgi vaqtda turli yoshdagi bemorlarda perioperatsion davrda pro- va anti-yallig'lanish sitokinlarining ajralib chiqishi haqida juda kam ma'lumot mavjud. Bizga ma'lum bo'lganidan, aortokoronar shuntlash operatsiyasini o'tkazgan bemorlarda sitokinlar darajasining yoshga qarab qanday o'zgarishini o'rganadigan tadqiqotlar mavjud emas.

Tizimli yallig'lanish reaksiyasi (o'tkir fazali javob reaksiyasi) rivojlanishi jarayonida sitokinlar tarmog'i neyroendokrin, immun, qon ishlab chiqarish va boshqa tizimlar o'rtasidagi aloqachi rolini o'ynaydi, bu esa yagona himoya reaksiyasini tashkil qilishga yordam beradi. Avvalo, sitokinlar mahalliy himoya reaksiyalarining rivojlanishini tartibga soladi, yallig'lanish reaksiyasini shakllantiradi. Agar mahalliy reaksiyalar yetarli bo'lmasa, yallig'lanish jarayoni davom etadi, sitokinlar ishlab chiqarilishi oshadi va ular qon aylanishiga tushib, endi tizimli darajada ta'sir qilishi mumkin (D.S. Shtashkevich, 2016). Adabiyotda, AKShni o'tkazgan bemorlarda operatsiyadan keyingi asoratlar rivojlanishida TNF-a, IL-6, IL-10, IL-1 kabi sitokinlarning roli haqida ma'lumotlar mavjud, ammo bu sitokin faolligi haqidagi ma'lumotlar qisqa kuzatuv davri (operatsiyadan keyin 24 soatgacha) tufayli aniq holatni aks ettirmaydi. Boshqa tadqiqotlarda esa aortokoronar shuntlash tufayli shikastlangan miokard tomonidan pro-yallig'lanish sitokinlar (TNF-a, IL-6) ishlab chiqarilishi haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Tadqiqotchilar bir fikrga kelishadiki, operatsiyadan keyingi asoratlar bilan og'riq bemorlarda immun javobning rivojlanishi pro-yallig'lanish yo'l orqali amalga oshadi [1,5,8].

Sitokinlar holatini aniqlash prognoz qilishda muhim ahamiyatga ega, chunki pro- va anti yallig'lanish sitokinlar darajasi, ularning nisbatlari alternativ-destruktiv va regeneratsiya-qayta tiklanish jarayonlarining intensivligini, kasalliklarning dinamikasini va rivojlanishini aks ettiradi. Mikrosirkulyatsiya holati va sitokinlar naqshining o'zaro bog'liqligi masalasi, ular to'g'ridan-to'g'ri yoki bilvosita mikrooqim holatiga ta'sir qilishi mumkinligi hozirgacha yetarlicha o'rganilmagan. Tabiiyki, bu o'zaro aloqalarni tushunish, davolash ta'sirlari (masalan, lazeroterapiya)dan keyingi jarayonlarni aniqlash va o'rganish uchun yordam beradi [7,9].

Sun'iy qon aylanishi va kardiojarrohlik odatda neytrofillarning va pro-yallig'lanish sitokinlarining faollashuvi va ajralib chiqishini keltirib chiqaradi [6], birinchi navbatda IL-6 va IL-8, ular esa operatsiya vaqtida yurakni ochish jarayonidan keyin poliorganli disfunktsiyaning erta prognozi sifatida qabul qilinadi. Shu bilan birga, ma'lumki, ultrafiltratsiya orqali yallig'lanish

moddalarini, shu jumladan yallig'lanish sitokinlari va toksinlarni qon aylanishidan chiqarib tashlash, operatsiyadan keyingi davrda yurak jarrohligi amaliyoti o'tkazilgan bemorlarda organlar funksiyasini yaxshilashga yordam berishi mumkin [2, 4]. IL-6, IL-8 va TNF- α transkripsiyasi ikkilamchi hodisa bo'lib, bioaktiv IL-1 beta tomonidan induktsiya qilinadi, bu yerda proteaz ingibitorlari bo'lgan ulinasatin, neytrofil elastazasini va pro-interleykin 1 beta (pro-IL-1 β ; 31 kDa peptid, faol bo'lmagan)ni IL-1 beta (17 kDa peptid, faol)ga aylantirishni kamaytiradi [11] va bu o'tkir fazali javob reaksiyasini kuchsizlantirishi mumkin.

Kardioxirurgik operatsiyadan keyin ulinasatin neytrofillarning sekvestratsiyasi va faollashuvini pasaytiradi hamda normal postoperatsion sitokinlar darajasining oshishini kamaytirishi mumkin, bu esa tizimli yallig'lanish reaksiyasi sindromini, o'pka kapillyarlarining o'tish qobiliyatini va postoperatsion o'pka shishini kamaytiradi. Ushbu natijalar, ulinasatin qabul qilgan bemorlarda oksigenatsiya indeksining yuqoriligini va tezkor ekstubatsiya vaqtini korrelyatsiya qiladi, bu esa reanimatologlarning bemorlarini sun'iy nafas olishdan tezda chiqarishga qaratilgan yanada agressiv siyosatni natijasidir. Bundan tashqari, ekstubatsiya vaqtini qisqartirish sun'iy nafas olish bilan bog'liq zotiljamdan himoya qilishi hamda reanimatsiya va intensiv terapiya bo'limida qolish davrini qisqartirishi, shifoxonada davolanish narxini kamaytirishi, bemor uchun ruhiy va jismoniy xavflarni, hatto o'limni kamaytirishga yordam berishi mumkin [8, 9].

Qiziqarli tomoni shundaki, bizning tadqiqotimizda ulinasatinning umumiy dozasiga nisbatan guruhlar tahlili ko'rsatdi-ki, yuqori dozali protokol ekstubatsiya vaqtini sezilarli darajada qisqartirdi, bu ulinasatinning o'pka himoyasiga doza bilan bog'liq ta'sirini ko'rsatishi mumkin. Ushbu savolga javob berish uchun yuqori sifatli tasodifiy, nazoratli tadqiqotlar talab qilinadi [11].

Ulinasatinning ekstubatsiya davrini qisqartirishi bemorlarni reanimatsiya va intensiv terapiya bo'limida qolish vaqtini kamaytiradi va ulinasatin terapiyasi bilan intensiv terapiya bo'limida qolish davomiyligini qisqartiradi. Shu nuqtada, 12 BioMed Research International tomonidan ko'rsatilgan ma'lumotlar kardiojarrohlikdan keyin intensiv terapiya bo'limida bemorlar qolish davomiyligiga ta'sir qiluvchi omillarni ko'rsatadi, bu omillar bir oz murakkab, ular orasida bemorning oldingi yurak funksiyasi, sun'iy qon aylanish davomiyligi, asosiy organlar funksiyasining tiklanishi, yangi boshlanadigan bo'lmacalar fibrillyatsiya, mexanik klapani tutilishi, postoperatsion qon ketish va noma'lum patogenetik omillar mavjud. Ushbu omillar tasodifiy nazoratli tadqiqotlar doirasida teng taqsimlanishi kerak [12,14].

Shuningdek, ulinasatinning postoperatsion ta'siri haqidagi qarama-qarshi xabarlar intensiv terapiya bo'limida qolish haqidagi tadqiqotlarga ta'sir qilishi mumkin, chunki ba'zi tasodifiy nazoratli tadqiqotlarda intensiv terapiya bo'limidan chiqarish standartlari aniqlanmagan yoki postoperatsion asoratlarga oid xabarlar mavjud emas [2, 5]. Ulinasatin, shuningdek, postoperatsion troponin - cTnI darajalarini sezilarli darajada kamaytiradi. Umuman olganda, jarrohlik amaliyotlari va sun'iy qon aylanishi kardiojarrohlikda tizimli o'tkir yallig'lanish reaksiyasini keltirib chiqaradi va miokardning shikastlanishini rivojlantiradi, bu esa endoteliyning o'tkazuvchanlik qobiliyatining oshishiga va qon tomirlari va parenximasining erkin radikallar bilan shikastlanishiga olib keladi, shuningdek, miokardning shikastlanishiga sabab bo'ladi. cTnI va KFK-MB miokard shikastlanishining prognoz indikatorlari bo'lib, cTnI miokardning eng kichik shikastlanishlarini eng yuqori kardiospetsifiklik bilan aks ettiradi, KFK-MBga qaraganda cTnI darajasining pasayishi ulinasatinning miokardni himoya qilishdagi potentsial rolini ko'rsatishi mumkin, ammo klinik natijalar (masalan, postoperatsion miokard ishemiyasi soni) aniqlanmagan.

Yaqinda, ko'proq dalilli ma'lumotlar ulinasatinning postoperatsion o'lim va kasallanishdagi rolini ko'rsatmoqda, ammo qarama-qarshi natijalar mavjud. Ushbu tadqiqotlarni talqin qilish qiyin, chunki ularning ichida kardioxirurgik aralashuvlar turi, sun'iy qon aylanish davomiyligi va ulinasatin dozasiga nisbatan sezilarli farqlar mavjud. Aniqlangan cheklovlar bo'lmaganda, infarkt miokard kabi asoratlarni kuzatish haqidagi ma'lumotlar past bo'lishi mumkin, bu esa shifoxonadagi o'lim darajasi va postoperatsion asoratlarni baholashda meta-analitik yondashuvning qiymatini cheklaydi [9].

Shunday qilib, tahlil qilish natijalariga ko'ra, ulinasatin yurak va o'pka funksiyalarini himoya qiluvchi ta'sir ko'rsatishi, cTnI darajalarini pasaytirishi, oksigenatsiya indeksini oshirishi va ekstubatsiya vaqtini qisqartirishi mumkin. Ushbu ta'sirlar neytrofil elastazasining pasayishini va

odatda yurak jarrohligi operatsiyasidan keyin birinchi postoperatsion kunda aniqlanadigan pro-yallig'lanish sitokinlar darajasining oshishining susayishi bilan bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin.

Ko'plab tadqiqotlarda ulinasatining yallig'lanishga qarshi va himoya qilish ta'siri o'rganilgan, shuningdek, u mukozali tripsin ingibitori sifatida ishemik-reperfuzion organ shikastlanishlariga qarshi kurashda samarali bo'lishi ko'rsatilgan [5,7]. Ularning natijalari, ulinasatin neytrofillarning infiltratsiyasini susaytirishi va neytrofillar tomonidan ishlab chiqarilgan elastaza va kimyoviy mediatorlarning chiqishini kamaytirishi mumkinligini ko'rsatadi [8,10]. Boshqa klinik tadqiqotlarda ulinasatining sun'iy qon aylanishi-induksiya qilgan pro-yallig'lanish sitokinnarning chiqishini va yurak-o'pka disfunktsiyasini pasayishidagi ta'sirlari, shuningdek, postoperatsion davrda barqaror gemodinamikani ta'kidlashgan [11]. Biroq, bu tadqiqotlarda ulinasatining yurak, o'pka va buyraklarning postoperatsion disfunktsiyasiga ijobiy ta'siri, yurakda operatsiya vaqtida pro-yallig'lanish sitokinnarning chiqishi kamayishi bilan bog'liq holda to'liq baholangan emas.

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Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

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